

Building an inclusive bioeconomy: Addressing gender, age, and socio-cultural barriers for a just transition[☆]

Gülşah Yilan^{a,*}, Andrea M. Bassi^b, Edvin Andreasson^b, Marco Bianchi^c,
Susanna Albertini^d, Valentina Vavassori^d, Piergiuseppe Morone^{a,e}

^a Bioeconomy in Transition Research Group, UnitelmaSapienza University of Rome, Rome 00161, Italy

^b KnowlEdge Srl, Olgiate Olona 21057, Italy

^c TECNALIA, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Astondo Bidea, Derio, Bizkaia E-48160, Spain

^d FVA New Media Research, Rome 00124, Italy

^e Corvinus Institute for Advanced Studies (CIAS), Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest 1093, Hungary

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ABSTRACT

Towards a circular bio-based economy, a just transition is critical to guarantee equitable distribution of benefits and prevent the exclusion of certain groups. Transition is inherently complex and requires comprehensive assessments of its multi-dimensional impacts. However, current evaluation frameworks often prioritise economic and environmental factors while neglecting social indicators, including equity, inclusion, and well-being. This gap calls for transdisciplinary approaches, merging insights from social sciences, humanities, and natural sciences to co-develop solutions. Accordingly, this paper aims to understand how socio-cultural dimension influence the transition. Building on a literature review, dynamic modelling, and indicator collection, we investigate more precisely the gender and age aspects of a just transition. The key aspects identified are related to the absence of a gender perspective in public policymaking and research, and the shortcomings in educational frameworks for fostering critical bioeconomy literacy among diverse age groups. Addressing these gaps requires a multi-pronged strategy including the promotion of behavioural change, building knowledge-sharing networks, policy integration with gender and intersectionality perspectives, and inclusive and resilient business models. Finally, adopting a holistic approach to boost the transition in the right direction can foster greater inclusivity and create a more balanced and sustainable bioeconomy landscape, benefiting diverse communities and stakeholders.

Societal impacts

The concept of a “just transition” originated in the 1970s as a labour protection strategy and has since been taken up more widely in climate and policy debates. It has regained particular prominence in international climate policy over the last decade, including explicit recognition in the Paris Agreement and in ILO guidance as a framework to pursue climate goals while promoting social inclusion [1–3]. The just-transition concept intersects with related ideas such as the circular economy, the bioeconomy, and the circular bioeconomy. The circular economy is a model of production and consumption that extends product and material lifetimes and couples socio-economic benefits with reduced environmental impacts [4]. The bioeconomy covers the use of biological

resources to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy and services and shares overlapping socio-economic concerns with just-transition thinking and is increasingly framed with circularity at its core [5]. Integrating just transition principles is therefore crucial for developing strategies that increase competitiveness, stimulate innovation, promote economic growth, and create jobs. A just circular bio-based transition implies that the shift toward a more sustainable economy must be fair, equitable, and inclusive: the benefits of circular bioeconomy pathways should be shared broadly so that no group is left behind or disproportionately disadvantaged [6].

The just transition is inherently complex and requires a comprehensive assessment of its multi-dimensional impacts. However, current evaluation frameworks often prioritise economic and environmental

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* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: gulsah.yilan@unitelmasapienza.it (G. Yilan).

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factors while neglecting crucial social indicators, including equity, inclusion, and well-being. This gap highlights the pressing need for transdisciplinary approaches that merge insights from social sciences, humanities (SSH), and natural sciences to co-develop solutions for fostering a just transition. The SSH perspective highlights that demographic characteristics, including age and gender, significantly influence individuals' willingness and capacity to engage with sustainable practices. Consumer psychology, behavioural economics, and labour studies help elucidate why cultural and social barriers, such as resistance to changing consumption habits, insufficient workforce diversity, and knowledge gaps, hinder the transition.

In this study, the main focus is on the gender and age aspects in a just circular bio-based transition. It is worth mentioning that Gender Equality is not only a fundamental human right but also defined as a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world [7]. In the scope of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), SDG 5 aims to achieve gender equality by ending all forms of discrimination, violence and any harmful practices against women and girls. Additionally, gender equality is an overarching goal that has strong connections with several other SDGs such as SDG1, 2,3,4,6,8,10, 11, and 16, spanning from access to an adequate standard of living to equal protection.

Against this background, this study revisits and analyses the findings of the SUSTRACK Horizon Europe project through a social lens, with specific attention to gender and age dimensions. In SUSTRACK, we conducted a comprehensive literature review to identify the main barriers hindering the transition, used System Dynamics modelling to simulate various scenarios to foresee its implications, and collected an inventory of existing indicators to assess and monitor the transition. Building on this work, this study further explores the implications of a just circular bio-based transition, with particular emphasis on SSH perspectives, especially concerning gender and age aspects.

Methodology

Table 1 summarises the methods, along with their main objective, employed in SUSTRACK, and specifies how, in this study, these elements were analysed through an SSH perspective to explore more deeply the gender and age dimensions of a just circular bio-based transition.

Literature review

To ensure a comprehensive and systematic identification of the barriers to transition to a circular bio-based economy (CBBE), a robust search strategy was designed to capture relevant grey and white literature on the topic [8,12]. The selected types of grey literature included: technical and research reports; working papers; policy briefs and white papers; industry publications; EU project deliverables; action plans, roadmaps, and guidance documents; discussion papers; and position papers. Once grey literature was identified, a systematic review process

Table 1
Methods, main and specific objectives.

Approach	Main objective	Specific objective related to SSH	SUSTRACK reference
Literature review	Identification of a long list of barriers hindering the transition	Cultural barriers specific to gender and age aspects (e. g., lack of workforce diversity)	[8]
Dynamic modelling	Interpretation of the systemic repercussions of policy implementation	Long-term socio-cultural impacts on gender and age (e.g., gender-disaggregated employment trends)	[9]
Indicator collection	Evaluating and monitoring the progress of the transition	Specific indicators on the gender and age dimension (e.g., the percentage of women-led businesses in the bioeconomy)	[10,11]

was established. An adapted STEEP (Social, Technological, Economical, Environmental, Political) method was used to categorise the identified barriers into five "base" barrier clusters: (i) Cultural, (ii) Technical, (iii) Economic, (iv) Environmental, and (v) Governance, and an additional cluster, namely, (vi) Structural to categorise barriers of a more systemic and cross-factorial nature. In this study, we mainly focused on the cultural barriers that were defined as the ones related to consumer behaviour, perception, attitude, awareness, consumption trends and traditions, workers' skills, qualifications, education, age and gender, as well as barriers related to internal culture, processes, attitudes, actions, and governance of companies.

Dynamic modelling

An integrated, systemic modelling approach was used to identify, quantify and analyse the impact of the bio-based transition at the sectoral and national level. Systems Thinking (ST) and System Dynamics (SD) were used as foundations for this work [9]. These methodologies, respectively qualitative (ST) and quantitative (SD), were employed to understand the dynamic behaviour of the national complex systems. ST and SD focus on how the system structure, including feedback loops, delays, and non-linear relationships, influences behaviour. As a result, these methodologies allow us to better understand the systemic repercussions of policy implementation, in this specific case concerning the bio-based transition.

Further, the Green Economy Model (GEM), an integrated model built using SD, was used to forecast several indicators, under different scenarios, through 2050. Improvements were made to GEM to better represent industrial dynamics. Specifically, the Germany GEM incorporates models for the construction and plastics industries, while the Italy GEM incorporates a textiles industry model, and the Netherlands GEM incorporates a chemicals industry model. These sectoral models consider product demand, consumption patterns, material reuse and recycling, and employment generation. This integration enables analyses at both macro and sectoral levels, capturing the impacts of industry changes on national and industry GDP.

This modelling exercise relies on a combination of macroeconomic and sector-specific data inputs. At the macro level, GEM integrates projections on population (UN Population Division), GDP growth (IMF World Economic Outlook), household and government accounts (Eurostat), and land use and carbon stock dynamics (European Environment Agency, Eurostat). Energy-related inputs include the national energy balance, fuel and electricity prices (International Energy Agency and Eurostat), and carbon and air pollutant emission factors (European Environment Agency, Eurostat). For the industry-specific models parametrized at the country level, detailed inputs are required for demand (e.g. building stock, for the construction sector), production process (e.g. value added, but also material and energy use for plastics production), and materials management (e.g. with the amount of waste generated, and the share of such materials being recycled, reused or landfilled for textile products). Data sources are sectoral, including Eurostat, EEA and national statistics agencies (e.g. Destatis, Industria Italiana) and academic studies. Comprehensive data inputs, detailed information on GEM [13], and the complete set of scenario results [14] are already available online.

The simulation results suggest that the transition toward a circular bio-based economy (CBBE) can generate structural changes in economic activity that have important social implications. While the shift toward bio-based production and circular practices increases overall value creation relative to the Business-as-Usual pathway, it also changes the composition of economic activity across sectors. In particular, reduced reliance on conventional fossil-based materials and increased emphasis on bio-based production, recycling, and resource efficiency alter labour demand and the distribution of economic opportunities across industries.

These structural shifts have implications for employment patterns

and regional development. The expansion of bio-based industries, circular manufacturing, and biomass supply chains creates new opportunities in sectors such as sustainable forestry, agriculture, recycling, and bio-based manufacturing. At the same time, reduced activity in some conventional industries may require labor reallocation and targeted support for affected workers and communities. These dynamics highlight the importance of policies that facilitate skills development, reskilling, and equitable access to emerging employment opportunities.

From an inclusion perspective, the transition also interacts with existing gender, age, and sociocultural barriers in labour markets and rural economies. Emerging bioeconomy value chains may create new livelihood opportunities, particularly in rural areas where biomass production and land restoration activities expand. However, ensuring that these opportunities are accessible to women, youth, and marginalised groups requires complementary measures addressing barriers such as unequal access to land, finance, training, and participation in value chains. Integrating these considerations into bioeconomy policies can help ensure that the transition contributes to a more inclusive and socially just development pathway.

Indicator selection

A comprehensive review of indicators currently used to monitor progress towards a sustainable bioeconomy was conducted [10,15]. Several databases were consulted, including the database developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and currently used to feed the EU bioeconomy monitoring framework, as well as databases from EUROSTAT, FAO, and FADN.¹ In total, 574 indicators were identified across the three sustainability dimensions and used at different implementation levels (EU, national, regional, and farm/product level).

After identification, all indicators were systematically classified using the taxonomy developed within the SUSTRACK project. This taxonomy provides a harmonised structure for characterising bioeconomy indicators and includes, among other fields, the societal objective defined by the EU bioeconomy strategy addressed by each indicator, the SDG to which the indicator contributes, and the sustainability pillar it belongs to. The taxonomy also captures the degree of contribution to SDG targets (direct or indirect) and the expected relationship of each indicator with specific SDGs (synergies or trade-offs), based on evidence from existing literature [11].

This structured classification enabled a targeted extraction of indicators linked to social sustainability. By selecting taxonomy fields of a social nature, such as Societal Objective 1 (Food and Nutrition Security) or Societal Objective 5 (Strengthening European Competitiveness and Jobs), as well as SDGs strongly associated with social outcomes (SDG 4; SDG 5; SDG 8; SDG 10), it was possible to identify, group and quantify indicators directly relevant to key societal challenges addressed by the EU bioeconomy.

Through this approach, we obtained direct evidence of the current availability, measurement frequency and implementation level of social-related bioeconomy indicators across monitoring systems. This evidence reveals how social sustainability is currently captured (or underrepresented) in existing indicator sets at national, regional and farm or product level. A full overview of the classified indicators and their mapping to societal issues is available in the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool.²

¹ Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). Note that as of 2025, the Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN) is set to replace the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). The FSDN will build on the FADN's legacy, expanding its scope to cover not only farms' income and business activities but also information on their environmental and social sustainability performance.

² <https://circularbioeconomyindicatorsystem.shinyapps.io/SUSTRACK4/#>.

Results and implications

Socio-cultural barriers to the CBBE transition have been extensively discussed within the social sciences and humanities (SSH), including sociology, psychology, political science, economics, and ethics. While comprehensive reviews exist [8,12], this article focuses on barriers and implications linked to gender and age (Table 1).

In this context, a key barrier is “insufficient measures to ensure safe and fair working conditions”. Labour studies highlight how global supply chains and power imbalances foster exploitative environments, particularly for vulnerable groups. As an example, women in low-value production roles remain disproportionately exposed to harmful chemicals [8,12]. The transition to bio-based materials can reduce harmful chemical exposure and improve indoor air quality. Our GEM simulation results suggest that better waste management and reductions in single-use plastics can lead to lower rates of respiratory illness, especially in urban and lower-income settings. These outcomes underscore the need for inclusive environmental health policies. Political and ethical perspectives also point at this issue as a matter of corporate responsibility, framing safe work as a moral obligation.

Another critical barrier is the “lack of specialised knowledge and expertise in bio-based production”, which affects who accesses emerging jobs and who risks exclusion. While sectors like manufacturing—typically male-dominated—may contract, others like recycling, waste management, and circular textiles—where women are more represented—are expected to expand. Similarly, in textiles, where women form a large share of the workforce, formalising informal roles and shifting to bio-based production could transform rather than eliminate jobs [16]. Yet without inclusive hiring and reskilling, existing gender disparities may worsen. Ethical frameworks also stress embedding sustainability values in education and skill development.

The “lack of workforce diversity”, particularly across gender and age, reinforces structural inequalities with economic and governance implications. Women remain overrepresented in informal, lower-paid roles and underrepresented in technical and leadership positions. As the CBBE reshapes employment, women, often in lower-paid roles within textiles (or any industry) and waste management, could benefit from wage equity policies and skill development programs. Our modelling scenarios show a net job gain, with materials management growing faster than manufacturing declines. However, persistent wage gaps must be addressed through equitable pay and career pathways. On the other hand, women's participation and influence in sustainability transitions remain constrained by gendered occupational segregation. Despite often displaying stronger pro-environmental behaviours than men, in some cases, women may remain underrepresented in science, technology, and policymaking. Inclusive governance and access to resources are key to overcoming this imbalance.

Beyond formal employment, the CBBE also opens up entrepreneurial pathways, particularly for women. The growing demand for sustainable products, circular supply chains, and bio-based textiles presents opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), many of which are led by women [17]. However, without access to finance and investment, these entrepreneurs may remain excluded. Microfinance and inclusive funding mechanisms are critical to supporting women-led businesses and ensuring gender-equitable growth. Furthermore, women, who often act as primary household decision-makers, can significantly influence sustainable consumption patterns. Policies promoting extended product lifespans and reuse (especially in textiles and plastics) can shift household demand towards second-hand or upcycled goods. Still, affordability is a barrier—bio-based alternatives must be priced accessibly to reach lower-income households and drive widespread adoption.

Age also plays a significant role in shaping participation and equity in the CBBE. Older generations may resist circular practices due to ingrained consumption patterns and unfamiliarity with emerging technologies. In contrast, younger cohorts (Millennials, Gen Z) generally

show stronger environmental awareness and support for circular models. However, despite their engagement, they frequently face systemic barriers to entry in bio-based sectors. As mentioned above, a major challenge lies in the mismatch between education and labour market needs. Educational systems often fail to equip younger generations with the skills needed for employment in bio-based industries. As a result, even though emerging sectors favour adaptability and digital literacy—traits more common among younger workers—opportunities may benefit mid-career professionals who already possess industry-specific expertise. This dynamic may sideline youth in favour of mid-career professionals with more experience. Bridging this gap requires improved educational programs, intergenerational learning, and tailored engagement. Moreover, age-based economic disparities compound the issue. Differences in salary progression, savings capacity, and consumption patterns between generations mean that younger workers often face more precarious financial conditions. Without targeted support, these barriers could prevent younger people from fully participating in and benefiting from the transition.

These challenges intersect—structural inequalities affecting gender also impact age and other marginalised groups. Viewed through a political science lens, these barriers represent entrenched power dynamics that systematically exclude less powerful groups from decision-making and access to opportunity. Unless equity is actively pursued, benefits of the CBBE—such as high-skilled jobs—will continue to accrue to those already advantaged.

To counter this, robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are essential. The EU Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework (59 indicators) provides a macro reference but lacks focus on gender and age. Societal issues are addressed only under Objective 5 (competitiveness and jobs), and the indicators largely track employment and value added, offering limited insight into more complex inequalities. Without gender-sensitive and inclusive data, inequalities may persist, preventing the fair distribution of bioeconomy benefits. In many cases, indicators capable of capturing gender, social or intersectional dimensions of bioeconomy dynamics are either inconsistently reported across countries/regions or embedded within datasets that lack sufficient territorial or sectoral granularity. While footprint indicators help evaluate environmental impacts, they do not account for who participates in or benefits from transitions. To guide a just CBBE, we need gender-sensitive, age-inclusive, and intersectional metrics. Disaggregated data, by sex, age, socioeconomic status and other relevant categories, would allow policymakers to better understand differential impacts and to design targeted interventions that address structural disadvantage. Future research must prioritise developing these inclusive frameworks, ensuring the experiences of women, youth, and marginalised groups shape both policy design and implementation.

Ultimately, achieving a just transition to the circular bio-based economy requires a holistic and transdisciplinary approach that integrates technological innovation with social equity. Socio-cultural barriers—such as structural inequality in access to knowledge, power, and resources—must be addressed through targeted, inclusive policies. With strategic planning and inclusive monitoring, the CBBE can evolve into a balanced, resilient, and socially just economic model that benefits people across all demographics.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Gülşah Yilan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Edvin Andreasson:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Andrea M. Bassi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Marco Bianchi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Valentina Vavasori:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization,

Methodology, Conceptualization. **Susanna Albertini:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Piergiuseppe Morone:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Ethical

The Authors have read and follow the ethical requirements for publication in Societal Impacts and confirm that the current work does not involve human subjects, animal experiments, or any data collected from social media platforms.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used free versions of Grammarly and ChatGPT to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

- Piergiuseppe Morone is the Editor-in-Chief of Societal Impacts Journal.

Given his role as Editor-in-Chief, Piergiuseppe Morone had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to other editors to ensure an unbiased review process.

- Gülşah Yilan is among the Editorial Board Members of Societal Impacts Journal.

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